

Synthesis, reactivity and physico-chemical properties of novel chloro complex of nickel(II) containing benzoxazole ligand

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Abstract : New chloro complex of nickel(II) of the type $[(\mu\text{-Cl})_2\text{Ni}_2\{\eta^2\text{-(pbox)}\}_2]$ (1) has been synthesized by the interaction of nickel(II) chloride with {2-(*o*-hydroxyphenyl)}-benzoxazole (pboxH) in equimolar ratio (in refluxing EtOH). Further, it was treated with sodium salts of Schiff bases (sb) [sb = smabH and saphH], isopropoxide and aluminiumtetraisopropoxide and aryloxo- and alkoxo-salts in the presence of THF/pyridine to produce new hydrocarbon soluble mixed ligand complexes of the types : [(smab)Ni $\{\eta^2\text{-(pbox)}\}$] (2), [(sap)Ni $\{\eta^2\text{-(pbox)}\}$] (3), $[(\mu\text{-OPr}^i)_2\text{Ni}_2\{\eta^2\text{-(pbox)}\}_2]$ (4), $[(\mu\text{-OAr})_2\text{Ni}_2\{\eta^2\text{-(pbox)}\}_2]$ (5) and $[\{(\mu\text{-OPr}^i)_2\text{Al(OPr}^i)_2\}\text{Ni}\{\eta^2\text{-(pbox)}\}]$ (6). These new products have been characterized by spectroscopic [IR, electronic (UV-visible), FAB-mass] and magnetic studies. A tentative T_d geometry around nickel(II) are proposed.

Keywords : Nickel(II), benzoxazole, synthesis, spectroscopic studies.

Introduction

Later '3d' transition metal (Cr^{III}, Fe^{III}, Co^{II}, Cu^{II}) complexes containing Schiff bases and substituted benzoxazole ligands have recently been investigated in our laboratories¹, due to its biological, pharmacological, clinical and analytical applications. Simultaneously, photophysics and photochemistry of these ligands have been studied by other group of workers².

In view of the above facts, we are interested to investigate the synthetic route(s) for the isolation of transition metal complexes and their bonding characteristics; which is a part of our research program in continuation.

We, therefore, report herein the synthesis, reactions and characterization by spectral [IR, electronic (UV-visible), FAB-mass] and magnetic studies of nickel(II) complexes containing {2-(*o*-hydroxyphenyl)}-benzoxazole moieties as potential ligands.

Experimental

All chemicals used throughout the course of experimental work were of G.R. or AnalaR grade. Spectroscopic grade solvents were employed for recording the spectra. Benzene (B.D.H.), isopropanol (B.D.H.), tetrahydrofuran (Loba) and pyridine (Loba) were dried according to standard literature procedure. Aluminium isopropoxide³ was prepared by dissolving aluminium foil in isopropanol in the presence of HgCl as catalyst and refluxing it for ~6 h. Final product was purified by distillation (b.p. 95 °C). Analysis of compound for the quantitative determination of nickel was carried out by atomic absorption spectroscopy, GBC-932 AA. Aluminium content present in the bimetallic complex was determined after precipitating aluminium as its oxinate⁴. Chloride content was estimated by Volhard's method⁴. Isopropoxide content in the corresponding isopropoxy derivative was estimated by an oxidimetric method⁵. IR spectra (4000–400 cm⁻¹) were recorded as nujol mulls; whereas 400–200 cm⁻¹ spectrum was recorded in KBr pellets, using Perkin-Elmer 1000 FTIR spectrophotometer. Electronic spectra of the compounds were recorded in benzene and tetrahydrofuran/pyridine due to solubility problem on a Hitachi-220 spectrophotometer. Magnetic susceptibility measurements were made at room temperature (23.5 °C) by Gouy method. FAB-mass spectra of nickel(II) complexes were recorded on JEOL SX 102/DA-6000 mass spectrometer/data system using argon/xenon (6 kV, 10 mA) as the FAB-gas.

(A) Preparation of ligands :

(a) {2-(*o*-Hydroxyphenyl)}-benzoxazole (pboxH) :

The ligand {2-(*o*-hydroxyphenyl)}-benzoxazole was synthesized according to previously established literature methods⁶.

(b) Salicylidene-2-methyl-1-aminobenzene (smabH) :

The ligand smabH⁷ was prepared by refluxing (for ~6 h) equimolar amounts of *o*-toluidine (10.7 g, 100 mmol) and salicylaldehyde (12.21 g, 100 mmol) in methanol (~30 cm³). Further sodium salt of salicylidene-2-methyl-1-aminobenzene, Na(smab)¹ was prepared by dissolving equimolar amounts of sodium metals and salicylidene-2-methyl-1-aminobenzene in methanol.

Salicylidene-2-aminopyridine (sapH)⁸ has been prepared by above method. 2-Aminosodium phenolate [Na(O-

C₆H₄NH₂)], sodium isopropoxide [Na(OPrⁱ)], and sodium-tetraalkoxyaluminate [Na{Al(OPrⁱ)₄}] were reported⁹ by earlier methods.

(B) Synthesis of complex [(μ-Cl)₂Ni₂{η²-(pbox)}₂] (1) :

A freshly prepared aqueous ethanolic solution (50% ethanol, ~50 cm³) of nickel(II) chloride (3.376 g, 14.2 mmol) was added dropwise to a prestirred hot ethanol (~75 cm³) solution containing {2-(*o*-hydroxyphenyl)}-benzoxazole (3 g, 14.2 mmol) in 1 : 1 molar ratio, which produced light pink coloured precipitate [(μ-Cl)₂Ni₂{η²-(pbox)}₂] (1) (Scheme 1). The complex (4.195 g, 97%) so obtained, was digested (~1 h), filtered, washed with aqueous ethanol and dried at 100 °C under reduced pressure. The product on analysis was found to have Ni, 19.1%, Cl, 12.1%; (Calcd.) : Ni (19.3%), Cl (11.6%).

Scheme 1. Synthesis of [(μ-Cl)₂Ni₂{η²-(pbox)}₂] (1).

(C) Reactions of $[(\mu\text{-Cl})_2\text{Ni}_2\{\eta^2\text{-(pbox)}\}_2]$ (1) with Na(slab) :

To a stirred hot yellowish green suspension of monochloro $\{2\text{-(}o\text{-hydroxyphenyl)-benzoxazolato}\}$ -nickel(II) complex (0.350 g, 1.15 mmol) in tetrahydrofuran ($\sim 30\text{ cm}^3$), was added sodium salt of salicylidene-2-methyl-1-aminobenzene (0.230 g, 1.15 mmol) in equimolar ratio. The reaction mixture was allowed to reflux for ~ 1 h, during which the colour of the solution changed from yellowish green to green. The precipitated NaCl (0.057 g, 1.15 mmol) was removed by filtration. The solvent was removed from the filtrate under reduced pressure to afford solid product $[(\text{sab})\text{Ni}\{\eta^2\text{-(pbox)}\}]$ (2) (0.472 g, 99%) (Scheme 2) which was purified by recrystallization from a THF/ C_6H_6 mixture. Analysis of this derivative was found to be Ni, 12.0%; (Calcd.) : Ni (12.2%).

Similar procedure was used to isolate $[(\text{sap})\text{Ni}\{\eta^2\text{-(pbox)}\}]$

(3), $[(\mu\text{-OPr}^i)_2\text{Ni}_2\{\eta^2\text{-(pbox)}\}_2]$ (4), $[(\mu\text{-OAr})_2\text{Ni}_2\{\eta^2\text{-(pbox)}\}_2]$ (5) and $[(\mu\text{-OPr}^i)_2\text{Al(OPr}^i)_2]\text{Ni}_2\{\eta^2\text{-(pbox)}\}$ (6). The synthetic and analytical details of all these complexes are given in Table 1.

Results and discussion

The nickel(II) complex $[(\mu\text{-Cl})_2\text{Ni}_2\{\eta^2\text{-(pbox)}\}_2]$ (1) has been prepared by the interaction of nickel(II) chloride (hydrated) with $\{2\text{-(}o\text{-hydroxyphenyl)-benzoxazole}\}$ in refluxing ethanol in 1 : 1 molar ratio, followed by the addition of dilute solution of sodium acetate to produce bright yellow coloured precipitate, which can be represented as follows :

The obtained complex has been digested, filtered and

Scheme 2. Reactions of $[(\mu\text{-Cl})_2\text{Ni}_2\{\eta^2\text{-(pbox)}\}_2]$ (1) with various Schiff bases and alkoxy-/aryloxo-ligands.

Table 1. Synthesis, reaction and analytical data of monochloro nickel(II) complex of benzoxazole

Sl. no.	Reactants (g, mmol)	Products Found (Calcd.) Yield (%)	M.p. (°C)	Nature	Analysis (%) : Found (Calcd.)					
					Ni	C	H	N	Cl	Al
1.	NiCl ₂ ·6H ₂ O + Hpbox (3.376, 14.2) (3, 14.2)	[(μ-Cl) ₂ Ni ₂ {η ² -(pbox)} ₂] (1) 4.195 (4.32), 97	350–353 ^a	Light brown powdered solid	19.1 (19.3)	50.60 (50.28)	2.80 (2.63)	4.52 (4.60)	12.1 (11.6)	-
2.	1 + Na(smab) (0.350, 1.15) (0.268, 1.15)	[(smab) ₂ Ni{η ² -(pbox)}] (2) 0.543 (0.551), 99	305–307	Green powdered solid	12.0 (12.3)	68.1 (67.68)	4.20 (4.17)	5.92 (5.85)	-	-
3.	1 + Na(sap) (0.200, 0.66) (0.14, 0.66)	[(sap)Ni{η ² -(pbox)}] (3) 0.440 (0.459), 96	300	Brown powdered solid	12.1 (12.5)	65.0 (64.41)	3.70 (3.65)	9.34 (9.02)	-	-
4.	1 + Na(OPr ⁱ) (0.300, 0.98) (0.079, 0.99)	[(μ-OPr ⁱ) ₂ Ni ₂ {η ² -(pbox)} ₂] (4) 0.330 (0.322), 89	-	Yellowish green crystalline	19.1 (19.2)	63.52 (63.23)	5.20 (4.94)	4.80 (4.61)	-	-
5.	1 + Na(OAr) (0.378, 1.24) (0.163, 1.243)	[(μ-OAr) ₂ Ni ₂ {η ² -(pbox)} ₂] (5) 0.409 (0.469), 85	-	Brown powdered solid	15.33 (15.58)	60.89 (60.52)	4.31 (3.72)	7.93 (7.43)	-	-
6.	1 + Na{Al(OPr ⁱ) ₄ } (0.227, 0.75) (0.213, 0.75)	[[Al(OPr ⁱ) ₄]{Ni{η ² -(pbox)}] (6) 0.367 (0.396), 92	295	Light brown powdered solid	11.0 (11.04)	56.95 (56.42)	5.20 (6.77)	2.76 (2.63)	-	5.75 (5.07)

washed with aqueous ethanol, the final drying was done at ~100 °C under reduced pressure to produce yellow coloured, insoluble, non-volatile polymeric complex.

The complex was found to be insoluble in common organic solvents (such as C₆H₆, CCl₄, CHCl₃, *n*-hexane etc.). However, the complex can form adduct with THF and pyridine after a long stirring for ~8–12 h, whereas complex is soluble in DMF, DMSO, THF and pyridine.

The chloro complex was treated with sodium salt of various Schiff bases, soluble coloured complexes were obtained. However, reaction of the chloro complex in presence of an excess of proton donor solvents, such as alcohol leads to disproportionation :

(where R may be Prⁱ or Buⁿ etc.)

The polymeric [(Cl)Ni(OR)]_n product has been separated and characterized by elemental analyses, which corresponds to the reported¹⁰ value for these complexes. To avoid disproportionation, THF has been used as reaction medium instead of alcohol, the complex (1) treated with sodium salts of salicylidene-2-aminopyridine (sapH), Na(sap) and salicylidene-2-methyl-1-aminobenzene (smabH), Na(smab) in equimolar ratio in the mixture of benzene and THF :

(where sb = smabH or sapH)

Further, it was reacted with Na(OR), [where R = Prⁱ and Ar (Ar = NH₂C₆H₄⁻)] and Na{Al(OPrⁱ)₄} in 1 : 1 stoichiometric ratio :

All these complexes are coloured and soluble in organic solvent and have been purified by recrystallization in the mixture of THF/C₆H₆. The physical and analytical details are collected in Table 1.

IR spectral studies :

Infrared spectrum of newly synthesized chloro complex of nickel(II) containing benzoxazole moiety [(μ-Cl)₂Ni₂{η²-(pbox)}₂] (1) has been recorded in the range 4000–400 cm⁻¹ in nujol mull and for lower region, 400–200 cm⁻¹ recorded in KBr pellets. The IR spectrum ex-

hibit structurally significant absorption bands at 244–228 cm^{-1} for $\nu_{\text{Ni-N}}$, 271–259 cm^{-1} for $\nu_{\text{Ni-O}}$, 319–267 cm^{-1} for $\nu_{\text{Ni-Cl}}$ and 1612–1479 cm^{-1} for $\nu_{\text{C-N}}$.

The presence of IR absorption bands in the range 244–228 cm^{-1} have been assigned to $\nu_{\text{Ni-N}}$ vibrations in the complex. The vibrations in the range 271–259 cm^{-1} are attributed to $\nu_{\text{Ni-O}}$ vibration; which indicates that ligand is oxygen bonded. In addition to $\nu_{\text{Ni-N}}$ and $\nu_{\text{Ni-O}}$ bands. A band at 275 cm^{-1} is assigned for $\nu_{\text{Ni-Cl}}$ bridging vibrations, which is very close to the reported^{11,12} frequency at 265 cm^{-1} for $(\mu\text{-Cl})\text{Ni}$ bridging vibrations. This is characteristics for the presence of bridging chlorine in tetrahedral complex (Scheme 1).

The characteristic IR band for $\nu_{\text{C=N}}$ group has been reported at $\sim 1615 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ in benzoxazole. The peak for $\nu_{\text{C=N}}$ was observed at 1612 cm^{-1} for $[(\mu\text{-Cl})_2\text{Ni}_2\{\eta^2\text{-}(\text{pbox})\}_2]$ (1); shift in frequencies of the metal-ligand complex from that of the ligand suggest that the coordination is taking place through hetero 'N' atom of C=N group in the complex. The complex exhibits a band at $\sim 228 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ which has been assigned to benzoxazole moiety, in the metal complex. The IR frequencies of the phenolic -OH group of the ligand, $\{2\text{-}(o\text{-hydroxyphenyl})\}$ -benzoxazole is generally observed in the region 1248–1256 cm^{-1} , which get shifted towards 1257–1316 cm^{-1} , thereby indicating the bonding through phenolic oxygen atom after deprotonation of the phenolic -OH group in this ligand.

The complex (5) showed shift in the absorption bands in the range 1285–1270 cm^{-1} which is indicative of chemical bond formation between metal and phenolic oxygen¹³. The complexes, (4) and (6) exhibited frequencies in the range 1030 cm^{-1} and 1150 cm^{-1} characteristic for $\nu_{(\text{C-O})\text{Ni}}$ respectively. The bands observed at $\sim 1150 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ is possibly due to terminal isopropoxy groups⁹ and the bands at 1040 and 950 cm^{-1} are characteristic for bridging isopropoxy groups. Instead of these bands; bands at 700 cm^{-1} and 430 cm^{-1} have been assigned for $\nu_{\text{Al-O}}$ and $\nu_{\text{Ni-O}}$ respectively.

Electronic spectral studies :

The complexes of nickel(II) exhibit two common geometrical forms, octahedral and tetrahedral/square planar; which can be distinguished by transitions in the range of near IR to visible region of electronic spectra¹⁴. The octahedral nickel(II) complexes generally exhibit three transitions :

corresponding to absorption bands in the region $< 6000 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, 6000–7000 cm^{-1} and 14000–20000 cm^{-1} respectively. Tetrahedral nickel(II) complexes are attributable to charge transfer absorption tailing into the visible region to ultraviolet. It has been observed mainly in the

Table 2. UV-visible spectral data for various nickel(II) complexes

Sl. no.	Complexes	Transition (cm^{-1})			C.T. band	
		${}^3T_1(F) \xrightarrow{\nu_3} {}^2B_{1g}(T_d)$	${}^3A_{2g} \xrightarrow{\nu_3} {}^2T_{1g}(P)$		I	II
1.	$[(\mu\text{-Cl})_2\text{Ni}_2\{\eta^2\text{-}(\text{pbox})\}_2]^a$	–	25974 26525(sh)		29762	31250 33455 34073
2.	$[(\text{smab})\text{Ni}\{\eta^2\text{-}(\text{pbox})\}]^b$	19646 21552(sh)	26178		29940	33557
3.	$[(\text{smab})\text{Ni}\{\eta^2\text{-}(\text{pbox})\}]^c$	1988 123419(sh) 24038	26595		29851	33445
4.	$[(\text{smab})\text{Ni}\{\eta^2\text{-}(\text{pbox})\}]^b$	20000(sh) 21739	–		27777	42194
5.	$[(\text{smab})\text{Ni}\{\eta^2\text{-}(\text{pbox})\}]^b$	17241 20000(sh) 21739	–		27777	44444

^aSpectra recorded in DMF.

^bSpectra recorded in benzene-THF mixture.

^cSpectra recorded in THF solution.

Scheme 3. Fragmentation pattern of $[(\mu\text{-Cl})_2\text{Ni}_2\{\eta^2\text{-(pbox)}\}_2]$ (I) using FAB-mass spectrum.

Fig. 1. FAB-mass spectrum of $[(\mu\text{-Cl})_2\text{Ni}_2\{\eta^2\text{-(pbox)}\}_2]$.

complexes having coordinated bromide or iodide ions. The splitting of visible absorption bands is caused by spin orbit coupling which lifts the degeneracy of the $T_1(P)$ state. An other feature of the spectra of tetrahedral nickel(II) complex is relatively high intensities of the absorption bands. The planar geometry is most preferred for the nickel(II) complexes. However, it is capable of exhibiting tetrahedral geometry as well, specifically in high spin $3d^8$ system.

The electronic spectrum of $[(\mu\text{-Cl})_2\text{Ni}_2\{\eta^2\text{-}(\text{pbox})\}_2]$ (1) complex has been measured in DMF, which exhibit two types of bands, d-d transition bands and charge transfer bands (Table 2). The observed electronic absorptions in the range $25974\text{--}27174\text{ cm}^{-1}$, corresponds ${}^3A_{2g} \xrightarrow{\nu_3} {}^3T_{1g}(P)$ transitions; which is the characteristics for the octahedral geometry¹⁵⁻¹⁷ around nickel(II).

The transitions, ν_1 could not be measured as it come towards near IR region, which was out of range of the instrument used; whereas ν_2 could not be observed. The bands observed in the range of $28409\text{--}29940\text{ cm}^{-1}$ may be attributable to the charge transfer transitions from phenolate moieties to the central metal nickel(II) ($\epsilon \approx 13000\text{ dm}^3\text{ mol}^{-1}\text{ cm}^{-1}$). In addition to above bands, two intense peaks are also observed in the range $31250\text{--}34129\text{ cm}^{-1}$ which may be assigned to intraligand charge transfer transition ($\epsilon \approx 15000\text{ dm}^3\text{ mol}^{-1}\text{ cm}^{-1}$).

Magnetic studies : High spin nickel(II) complex show paramagnetism corresponding to two unpaired spin only value, $\mu_{s.o.} = 2.8$ B.M. The magnetic moment is generally observed in the range $3.5\text{--}4.2$ B.M. for tetrahedral geometry^{18,19}. This higher value of magnetic moment may be due to some orbital contribution²⁰. However, in the case of octahedral nickel(II) complex, magnetic moment value lie in the range $2.8\text{--}3.4$ B.M. Magnetic susceptibility measurements of $[(\mu\text{-Cl})_2\text{Ni}_2\{\eta^2\text{-}(\text{pbox})\}_2]$ (1) gives $\mu_{\text{eff}} = 3.48$ B.M., which is in quite agreement with the reported value²¹ tetrahedral geometry of the nickel(II) complex containing benzoxazole moiety. This value (3.48 B.M.) is in the lower end of the range given for tetrahedral geometry, possibly due to their polymeric nature.

FAB-mass studies :

The FAB-mass spectrum (Fig. 1) of a newly synthesized compound of nickel(II), $[(\mu\text{-Cl})_2\text{Ni}_2\{\eta^2\text{-}(\text{pbox})\}_2]$ (1) (Scheme 3), showed an important peak at $m/z = 608$, which correspond to molecular weight of the compound supported for the dimeric structure. Besides this peak of the complex showed the fragmentation ion peak at $m/z = 304$, indicated fragmentation of dimer molecule to mono-

mer¹. Other important peaks were observed as result of fragmentation of ligand from complexes by the formation of radical cations such as Cl^\cdot , $\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{O}^\cdot$ (I); $\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{O}^\cdot$, $\text{C}_7\text{H}_4\text{NO}^\cdot$, NiCl_2 (II); $\text{C}_7\text{H}_4\text{NO}^\cdot$, $\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{O}^\cdot$ (III).

A new and novel complex $[(\mu\text{-Cl})_2\text{Ni}_2\{\mu^2\text{-}(\text{pbox})\}_2]$ (1) of nickel(II) has been synthesized using bidentate benzoxazole ligand and characterized by spectroscopic and magnetic studies. The reactivity towards alkoxo- and aryloxo-groups and Schiff base ligands was observed. A novel bimetallic hydrocarbon soluble complex $[(\mu\text{-OPr}^i)_2\text{Al}(\text{OPr}^i)_2]\text{Ni}\{\eta^2\text{-}(\text{pbox})\}$ (6) is obtained as a result of the reaction of complex (1) with $\text{Na}\{\text{Al}(\text{OPr}^i)_4\}$ in 1 : 1 molar ratio, it has two metal centres bridged by isopropoxy groups. A definite conclusions regarding the structure of these complexes in solid state would be possible only after X-ray crystallographic studies, which have not been successful so far. However, formula of the complex (1) has been suggested by elemental analysis, spectral studies and confirmed by FAB-mass spectra showing multiplets representing successive degradation of the molecule (1) shown in Scheme 3 and was found to be dimeric.

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